

Moral knowing, moral feeling, and moral action in reflecting moral development of students in junior high school

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ABSTRACT

This research objective is to test the validity and reliability of moral development instruments on junior high school students. The moral development instrument for junior high school students was developed based on three aspects of moral development: moral knowing, moral feeling, and moral action. This research sample involves 172 students at Junior High School "X" in Magelang City, Indonesia ranging from 12 to 15 years of age. The total items developed from the three aspects are 152 items consisting of 60 items of moral knowing, 62 items of moral feeling, and 30 items of moral action. The items analysis was calculated using the product moment correlation technique and corrected item-total correlation technique. This research result indicates that the moral development instrument is valid with the score of $r_{count} > r_{table}$ and stated reliable with Cronbach alpha score of moral knowing is 0.876, moral feeling is 0.886, and moral action is 0.830. The validity and reliability test result shows that the moral development instrument for students is feasible to use. Moral knowing, moral feeling, and moral action can reflect students' moral development.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The moral is one of the crucial intelligence that significantly affects human life [1]. Moral development is vulnerable in adolescence, so they require moral guidance to develop appropriately for the progress of the nation and state [2], [3]. Adolescence is a transition period from childhood to adulthood, a developmental stage in human life [4]. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), adolescents are individuals aged from 10-19 years. In Indonesia, the population rate in the productive category rises in the age range between 15-19 years, with a total of 22.29 million in 2019, 22.31 million in 2020, and 22.21 million in 2021 [5]. The high rates of adolescent growth create changes in the order of life. There is a shift in life that is more practical, simple, effective and digitized with the support of rapid technological developments [6], [7]. This positive impact is not without adverse effects from high technological developments, such as increasing crime rates, drug abuse, rampant alcohol consumption in adolescents, and promiscuity behavior among young men and women [8], [9]. This shift in behavior is caused by moral decadence that is not accompanied by concrete preventive measures, so the tendency for adolescent moral decline will increase [10].

Piaget alluded to moral development in adolescents that morals are individual attitudes and behavior when they can solve the processes that occur in the cognitive, their actions conforming to the applied values

within the environment [11], [12]. A person's moral development will be reflected in their reasoning process corresponding to the moral development stages [13]. According to Hurlock [14], the task of adolescent development is related to the problem of developing moral values corresponding to the environmental norms that adolescents will enter. The community environment can be a place for teenagers to learn about their moral development [15]. Moral development in adolescents can provide an assessment of what can and cannot be done corresponding to society's applicable norms and rules [16], [17]. Aspects of moral development, according to Syamsu [17], include moral knowing, which this stage aims to give control to adolescents related to values; the moral feeling is defined by strengthening the emotional (affective) aspect so that adolescents grow into individuals with character; moral action is determined by activities or implementations carried out by adolescents based on applicable values and norms [18]. Moral development conforming to the stages will bring merit to the environment with good character and provide goodness for other people's life quality [16].

Conditions in the community show adolescents' moral degradation, indicated by crime increasing by 15% in 2021, abortions rate reaching 700-800 thousand in adolescents, as many as 52 thousand people are infected by HIV, out of which 70% is adolescent, drug abuse, and death due to drugs primarily by adolescent [4]. Based on the data explanation, it is stated that the current social situations within the community, especially among adolescents, are massively experiencing moral decadence. The occurrence of moral decadence includes sophisticated technological advancement that presents both positive and negative information, the fading faith quality of the younger generation that triggers criminal behavior and social crimes in society, and the waning of moral formation and development.

Moral decadence is a decrease in behavioral awareness according to applicable rules due to a lack of understanding of obeying the law and human conscience values [17]. From time to time, the younger generation's morals have decreased in quality and are allowed to continue to decline. It is characterized by increased violence against adolescents, use of bad words, strong peer group influence in acts of violence, low respect for teachers and parents, promiscuity behavior, illicit drug abuse, decreased work ethic, habituation of cheating and dishonesty, mutual suspicion and hatred among others, resulting in a low sense of responsibility for individuals and citizens [19].

The phenomenon is a huge concern for this nation, so we need better debriefing and education for students' moral development for this nation to progress in the future [20]. The problem in assisting moral development in Indonesia is that there are currently no tools to help students practically and independently identify their moral level. Therefore, researchers want to develop an application that can measure students' morals on a computer-based scale to be more flexible and easy to use and become a tool for counseling practitioners to identify adolescents' moral levels more easily and practically.

Currently, adolescents with problems who need help identifying morals still have to come and be counseled by counselors and counseling guidance teachers. In addition, the tools used to determine student problems can still not specifically identify students' morals. The existing tools currently used to identify individual developmental levels are called developmental task inventory (ITP), problem checklists (DCM), and problem-solving tools (AUM) are tools used to assess too broad aspects. These tools' weakness is that they have not been able to reveal morals specifically. The arrangement of students' moral development instruments is based on the theory developed by Piaget and Kohlberg by using three aspects consisting of moral knowing with indicators of moral awareness, knowing the moral values of perspective taking, moral reasoning, decision making, and self-understanding; moral feeling describes indicators of conscience, self-esteem, empathy, loving-kindness, self-control, humility; and moral action with indicators such as moral competence, will, and habits [15]. This research objective is to test the validity and reliability of adolescent moral development instruments.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

The method used in the study is research and development, which then produces a research instrument product that will test the tool's accuracy and consistency [21]. This study involved 172 students at Junior High School "X" in Magelang City, Indonesia. The total population in this study was 658 students. Based on Slovin's formula, the number of samples met the criteria for determining a sample size of at least 10% of the total population. The scale arrangement is based on aspects that refer to Lickona's theory [15], consisting of moral knowing, moral feeling, and moral action. Based on these three components, the researcher compiled a scale with 152 items with details: 60 items for the moral knowing aspect, 62 items for the moral feeling aspect, and 30 items of moral action.

The measurement scale used is a Likert scale with five answers categories over a statement; that is, a strongly disagree statement is given one score, disagree is given a two score, somewhat agree is given a three score, agree given a four score, and strongly agree was given a five score on the favorable statement while the unfavorable statements with the opposite weight. The indicators reflecting each aspect are described in Table 1, and the blueprint for the adolescent moral scale is shown in Table 2. A detailed explanation of the moral knowing scale is shown in Table 3, the moral feeling scale is in Table 4, and the moral action scale is in Table 5.

Table 1. Aspect and indicator of adolescent moral

No	Aspect	Indicator
1	Moral knowing	Moral awareness Knowing moral values Perspective-taking Moral reasoning Decision making Understanding oneself
2	Moral feeling	Conscience Self-esteem Empathy Loving-kindness Self-control Humility
3	Moral action	Moral competence Will Habit

Table 2. Blueprint of students' moral development scale

No	Aspect	Indicator	No. item		Σ
			Favorable	Unfavorable	
1	Moral knowing	Moral awareness	4, 5, 6, 8, 9	1, 2, 3, 7, 10	10
		Knowing moral values	11, 13, 15, 17, 19	12, 14, 16, 18, 20	10
		Perspective-taking	21, 22, 24, 25, 26	23, 27, 28, 29, 30	10
		Moral reasoning	31, 32, 33, 35, 39	34, 36, 37, 38, 40	10
		Decision making	41, 42, 44, 45, 49	43,46,47,48,50	10
		Understanding oneself	51, 53, 54, 55, 59	52,56,57,58,60	10
2	Moral feeling	Conscience	61, 63, 65, 66, 69	62,64,67,68,70	10
		Self-esteem	71, 72, 74, 77, 79	73,75,76,78,80	10
		Empathy	81, 82, 84, 85, 89	83,86,87,88,90,91	11
		Loving-kindness	92, 94, 96, 97, 99, 101, 102	93, 95, 98, 100	11
		Self-control	103, 105, 107, 109, 111	104, 106, 108, 110, 112	10
		Humility	113, 114, 116, 117, 120,	115, 118, 119, 121, 122	10
3	Moral action	Moral competence	123, 125, 127, 129, 131	124, 126, 128,130,132	10
		Will	133, 134, 136, 137, 140	135,138,139,141,142	10
		Habit	143, 145, 147, 150, 152	144,146,148,149,151	10
		Total item			152

Table 3. Moral knowing scale

Dimension	Sub-dimension	Description	Indicator	Illustration
Moral knowing	Moral awareness	The ability to be aware of matters involved with moral issues and moral judgment	Knowing the difference between good and bad Following the prevailing moral rules Be polite to others Helping others	I know what is good and what is wrong
	Knowing moral values	The ability to respect life and freedom, responsibility, honesty, fairness, tolerance, courtesy, integrity, friendliness, compassion, and courage	Understanding moral values Understand the importance of behaving and comporting Responsible, fair, honest, and polite toward others	I, in my behavior, always uphold high moral values
	Perspective-taking	The ability to see from another's point of view	Seeing from a different point of view Not hasty to judge Correcting mistakes	I consider the views of others when going to take an action
	Moral reasoning	Skills related to an understanding of what morality is and why people should be moral	Understanding why people should be moral Understand what actions not to take	I understand why we must have good morals
	Decision making	The ability to make moral decisions	Making decisions with moral considerations Considering the risks of decision making Considering decisions fairly	I will make a decision when I have considered the existing moral values
	Understanding oneself	The ability to recognize and evaluate one's own behavior	Be able to make self-assessment Understand what it takes Conducting introspection of behavior	I can judge myself

Table 4. Moral feeling scale

Dimension	Sub-dimension	Description	Indicator	Illustration
Moral feeling	Conscience	The ability is divided into cognitive parts to see the truth, and emotional parts function to feel what is right	Helping and forgiving someone Do good and have a good attitude toward someone	I do good things with my emotional self-consideration
	Self-esteem	The ability to respect oneself	Thinking positively and being grateful Maintaining diet and body pattern Accepting one own strength and weaknesses	Taking care of oneself by always thinking positive
	Empathy	The ability to see experiences from the emotional side in perspective taking	Understanding others' feelings Listening and understanding others' situation	I try to understand other people's feelings before acting
	Loving-kindness	The ability in its highest form of a character who is interested in good things	Enjoying doing good Keeping promises and loving to share Helping people in need Grateful and happy for others' people happiness	I feel happy doing good deeds because I like doing good deeds
	Self-control	The ability to control oneself	Can control oneself Can control anger and speeches Not rashly in their actions	I can control myself in any situation
	Humility	The ability from the affective side of self-knowledge that is open to facts and the will to correct what is wrong	Accept when reprimanded Not demean people and accept criticism Forgiving and not arrogant Say thank you, and don't be shy about making mistakes	I accept being reprimanded when I do something wrong

Table 5. Moral action scale

Dimension	Sub-dimension	Description	Indicator	Illustration
Moral action	Moral competence	The ability to change feelings and moral judgments into effective moral action	Acted with consideration Following joint decision Thinking optimistically and doing good without expecting a reward Carrying out obligations and forgiving others	I always acted with rational considerations and feelings
	Will	The will to always be good	Be professional Carrying out obligations and completing priority activities	Putting responsibilities first is the leading affair for me
	Habit	The ability to turn good deeds into a habit	Speak well and honestly Saying gratitude and worship Respecting the older person Obeying the rules	I'm not afraid to tell the truth

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data analysis in this study consisted of a validity and reliability analysis of adolescents' morals. Competent experts validate through professional judgment before validation and reliability tests on measuring instruments. Expert validation is needed in this research to determine the instrument accuracy viewing from various aspects [22]. Item analysis is a technique used to examine items on a scale. The item analysis process is intended to eliminate inconsistent items.

3.1. Scale validity

In this study, the item validity test used the product moment correlation technique, carried out by correlating each score on the variable with the total score in each variable. The moral knowing aspect consists of 6 items, the moral feeling aspect consists of 6 items, and the moral action consists of 6 items. The results of the analysis of each aspect are shown in Table 6.

Table 6 describes several items that were developed on the moral knowing aspect. The validity test result is based on the calculations of the moral knowing dimension of 172 respondents, and it can be concluded that not all questions in the questionnaire are valid. In item no. 56, it is stated not valid ($r_{\text{count}} < r_{\text{table}}$) with the score of $r_{\text{count}}=0.115$ in which the score of $r_{\text{table}}=0.150$. The validity of the moral knowing dimension shifted from 0.151 to 0.524.

Table 6. Validity test of moral knowing aspect

No	Question item	Correlation coefficient score	Conclusion
1	I obey the morality prevailing in society	0.492	Valid
4	I know what is good and what is wrong	0.352	Valid
19	I know the importance of being careful in attitude and behavior	0.508	Valid
32	I understand that life must be based on values and morals	0.396	Valid
47	I dare to make the right decision when doing deliberation	0.466	Valid
56	I understand the advantages that I have	0.115	Not valid

Table 7 describes examples of items developed from moral feeling aspects. The validity test results on the moral feeling dimension to 172 respondents is that there are three invalid items or falls because of the correlation $r_{\text{count}} < r_{\text{table}}$, e.g., items 64, 102, 118 with r_{values} of 0.078, -0.036, and 0.048, respectively. The validity of the moral feeling dimension shifted from 0.185 to 0.564.

Table 7. Validity test of moral feeling aspect

No	Question item	Correlation coefficient score	Conclusion
62	I forgive friends who have done terrible things	0.401	Valid
72	I take care of myself by always thinking positive	0.411	Valid
102	I can control myself in any situation	-0.036	Not valid
103	I always do my duties before playing with friends	0.423	Valid
112	I am reluctant to tell others the good that I have done	0.442	Valid
118	I try to accept defeat gracefully	0.048	Not valid

Table 8 explains several items developed in the moral action aspect. The validity test results on the moral action dimension show that all items can be drawn to the same conclusion that all questions in the questionnaire are valid because the score of $r_{\text{count}} > r_{\text{table}}$ ($r_{\text{count}} > 0.150$) with the validity score shifting from 0.197 to 0.624. The invalid Items ($r_{\text{count}} < r_{\text{table}}$) are declared void and are not included in the further validity test stage. In the next step, the validation results of all items in the three aspects show that they are valid.

Table 8. Validity test of moral action aspect

No	Question item	Correlation coefficient score	Conclusion
124	I am happy to carry out my learning obligations from the teacher	0.415	Valid
127	For me, kindness can be manifested in many ways	0.348	Valid
133	I took the initiative to visit a friend who was sick	0.507	Valid
137	I will try to prevent friends who want to ditch class	0.326	Valid
138	For me, cheating is a sin	0.571	Valid
150	I always greet the teacher whenever I pass them at school	0.473	Valid

3.2. Reliability scale

The reliability test in this study uses Cronbach alpha coefficient statistics that will show whether the moral measurement scale for adolescents is reliable or not. The instrument was declared reliable if the Cronbach alpha coefficient score was ≥ 0.70 . The reliability test results show that the Cronbach alpha coefficient score for the moral knowing dimension is 0.876, the moral feeling dimension is 0.886, and the moral action dimension is 0.830. Because Cronbach Alpha coefficient score in each dimension is greater than 0.800, it can be concluded that the instrument is reliable and can be used as a data collection tool.

3.3. Discussion

The research analysis implies that the validity and reliability of test results of the adolescent moral scale with aspects that include moral knowing, moral feeling, and moral action are feasible to measure adolescents' moral levels. The adolescent moral scale shows that all dimensions and indicators of morals can reflect and shape adolescents' morals. Previous research that analyzed adolescents' moral scale stated that based on the results of the first-order and second-order CFA, they were overall fit or matched between theory and data in the field [18], [23].

In the moral knowing dimension, the item validity level ranges from 0.151 to 0.524 with a reliability of 0.876. This outcome is similar to the study [24], [25], stating that the reliability score of the moral knowing scale is 0.847. Subjects who have morals in the knowing dimension will be able to have the ability to recognize morals, know moral values, be able to take lessons from the point of view of others, understand morals, take a morally conscious attitude, and know themselves. [26], [27]. The other studies also support that moral knowing can be implemented so that adolescents can distinguish between right and wrong, prohibitions and

recommendations, and good and bad behavior [28]. Moral knowing can also help an adolescent form knowledge so that good characters and habits are formed [29]. In a study [30], the test to measure the moral intelligence scale in adolescents shows a reliability score with a Cronbach alpha value of 0.896. At the same time, other research [31] mentioned the reliability of moral development instruments is 0.865.

In the moral feeling dimension, the item validity level ranges from 0.185 to 0.564, with a reliability score of 0.886. This outcome is similar to other studies that measured the moral feeling scale and obtained a reliability of 0.932 [32]. Subjects who have a moral feeling dimension will be able to have the ability to feel through their conscience, have self-esteem, empathy, loving-kindness, self-control, and humility so that they can bring up good moral feelings [33]. Other researches support that the moral feeling scale can measure moral in an effective way in early childhood and involve participants directly in the measurement [1], [34].

In the moral action dimension, the item validity level ranges from 0.197 to 0.624, with a reliability score of 0.830. Similar to other studies that measure the moral feeling scale, which shows a reliability value of 0.951 [24]. Subjects with a moral action dimension will have the ability to have moral competence, the will or desire to do good, and the habit of doing good. Several studies [33], [35] explained that interventions that alter emotional responses could influence moral behavior. Other studies support that the moral action scale has items that contribute significantly to measuring the moral action construct [36]. In contrast to previous studies that measured the moral level of adolescents in general, this research is more specific and detailed, which measures based on three moral domains, moral knowing, i.e., moral feeling and moral action, and involving adolescents directly, students at Junior High School "X" in Magelang City.

A limitation in this research is that the number of items in the moral development instrument is too many, namely 152 items, this can have an impact on the filling process carried out by students needing to be more optimal. The sample used is still limited to domiciles at Junior High School "X" in Magelang City, so it is less diverse and does not provide a more comprehensive picture. This research implies that the validity and reliability of the measuring tool for moral development have been tested so that future researchers can reuse it in measuring the moral development of junior high school students in other locations.

Future researchers can use this tested moral development measuring tool to apply and introduce it to the education world in Indonesia with increasingly concise items that are easy to apply in line with the development of increasingly advanced measuring tools. In future research, it is also hoped that the samples obtained will come from various city domiciles to maximize the results. Apart from that, further researchers can test its validity and reliability using more precise and detailed methods such as construct validity and construct reliability.

4. CONCLUSION

This study aims to test the validity and reliability of the adolescent moral scale. Adolescents' moral scale can be reflected in three forming aspects, moral knowing, moral feeling, and moral feeling. The analysis results of the validity and reliability tests show that the moral scale in adolescents is valid and reliable for measuring moral development levels in adolescents. Therefore, in measuring adolescent morals, it is necessary to use an adolescent moral scale that not only measures morals in general but also in three dimensions: moral knowing, moral feeling, and moral action.

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